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Online-Learning Challenges Faced During in the COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

Type or paste your abstract here as prescribed by the journal's instructions for authors. COVID-19 has wreaked havoc on the majority of the world's industries. In most places around the world, education seems to be the only industry that has entirely transitioned to an online method. During the epidemic, online learning was the best option for continuing education, especially in tertiary education. The goal of this research is to find out what issues and obstacles English language learners face in their daily lives. The purpose of this study is to investigate the viability of virtual learning methods by evaluating the learners' unique experiences in online education. This is accomplished by examining the responses of 100 students to a survey-based questionnaire. The study's validity was tested using a descriptive statistical method. The key issues that influence and effect online learning during COVID-19 are connected to technological, academic, and communication concerns, according to the findings. The findings of the survey demonstrate that the majority of learners are dissatisfied with continued online learning since they are not making the significant progress in language learning.

Keywords: COVID-19 Pandemic, learning challenges, Online learning

1. Introduction

Because of the rapid advancements in technology, schooling has to be updated. They needed to be able to learn anywhere at time and from any location. Wolfinger (Wolfinger, 2016). Some global institutes have implemented online learning throughout the last two decades. Most institutions, colleges, and universities, on the other hand, do not use this educational style, and their personnel is unaware of what e-learning entails. MOOCs (Massive Online Open Courses) have made online learning and participation more accessible to academics (Lynch, 2004). The use of advice to inspire students in virtual learning is dependent on a practical understanding of cognitive, emotional, and behavioral involvement (Hartnett and Louwrens, 2015). In such a critical crisis as the transition to a new educational environment, learners require extra social support to boost their concentration and motivation for online learning (Eccles et al., 1993; Harter, Whitesell, & Kowalski, 1992; Midgley, Anderman, & Hicks, 1995; Roeser & Eccles, 1998).

The global decision to shut down educational institutes was sensible in order to maintain social distance and prevent the spread of the disease. Because they were previously prepared for online learning, some countries shifted to online learning right away. All universities in Saudi Arabia used the Blackboard technology for distance education and delivered a variety of optional and general courses.

This study looked at the challenges and obstacles faced by university students during in the current global pandemic, as well as the possible resources and solutions that could be provided in the future to address these issues. The purpose of this study is to look into the impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on the learning process. In the post-Covid-19 crisis, the shape of the dangerous transition will manifest itself in all society

institutions, particularly in the educational sector. These changes necessitate the creation of guidelines by competent leaders for redefining the direction of all industries. . Starting with education, university education will play a critical part in this process, followed by the healthcare sector, economics, sports, and so on. An unguided plan, on the other hand, will result in failure and uncertainty. During the new corona virus crisis, most countries around the world saw extraordinary responses and efforts from the clinical and academic sectors, and India is one of them. Because of the severity of the circumstances caused by the COVID-19 outbreak, the only choice was to switch to online learning. The lockdown is used in most states to protect society from an outbreak of the new corona virus. On March 2, 2020, Indian University was allowed to commence online learning. The university's previous experience with blended learning prior to COVID-19 aided the pandemic's swift shift to e-learning. Prior to the corona virus outbreak, blended learning was implemented in all university colleges with certain general or elective subjects using the Blackboard platform. As a result, some faculty members gained valuable expertise using the Blackboard technology for online education. These professors arranged training seminars on how to use Blackboard for online teaching for their colleagues at their colleges. The university's training and development section organized a series of online practice sessions for all of the university's faculty members in various colleges and branches. There are certain pros and cons to online learning; for example, online education is accessible worldwide, and it saves time, money, and effort. When students want lecturers to record classes, one benefits of internet learning is the ability to record lectures. Teachers are thoroughly evaluating and preparing for recording, which has a positive impact on teaching tactics and procedures. Students are able to access the lectures at any time and gain a deeper understanding of the material. Writing,

speaking, and reading obstacles were among the difficulties encountered in English language skills as well as other English courses. For linguistics classes that need the teacher to teach phonetics, allophones, morphemes, and other concepts to students face to face, such as pronunciation and phonology challenges. Not all students have reliable internet access. Some students had network issues and lacked strong learning gadgets.

In times of crisis and difficulty, the impact of information technology (IT) and the COVID-19 pandemic in accelerating present and future e-learning entrepreneurial activation is seen as a remedy.

The research provides answers to the following questions:

- Q1. What are the difficulties of online learning, and what resources will be available to students during this time?
- Q2. Can learners in small areas with poor internet access benefit from online learning?
- Q3. How can online English classes be made more interesting, inspiring, and innovative? •
- Q4. Will students become comfortable with online platforms and have sufficient confidence and experience to continue their education online?

The following are the study's goals:

- Recognize the hurdles and roadblocks to e-learning that learners faced during the COVID-19 crisis.

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- Recognize and employ the most effective ways and modes for engaging and motivating e-learning students.
 - Educate students and teachers about the existing systems and tools that can help improve and reinforce education during pandemics.
 - Investigate the ramifications of the university's mass drive toward online learning.

2. Review of the literature

The following section summarises prior online learning research undertaken during the COVID-19 crisis, as well as research on online learning issues and educational technology. After the recent pandemic in India's basic education colleges, a survey was performed to assess students' perspectives on the field of digital learning. The students left the study with a positive view of digital education in higher education. The study's benefit is the suggestion for building and delivering courses on the use and use of mobile learning. The sample size (52 participants) in this study is insufficient to generalise m-learning in higher education (Alanezi & AlAzwani, 2020). During the COVID19 outbreak, another study looked into the challenges of online learning in medical education (Rajab, Mohammad, Gazal, & Alkattan, 2020). The study included 208 students and faculty members from Alfaisal University's College of Medicine in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. Communication, evaluation, online learning experience, technological use skills, goal setting, anxiety, and coronavirus sickness stress were all listed as problems in the study. Students, on the other hand, praised the effect of online education during the pandemic. Yildiz (2020) did a meta-analysis study on latest trend in educational technology from 2015 to 2020. Several aspects of the field were examined in the study. The study's findings showed that incorporating educational technology into teaching and learning is a good idea. The influence of the pandemic on

entrepreneurial education is discussed in an essay by editorial staff Liguori and Winkler (2020). More research and resources on the issues of online entrepreneurship education are needed, they said.

3. Framework for Thinking

Technology applications and digital literacy skills have been developed and strengthened (Coiro, Knobel, Lankshear, & Leu, 2008: p.4). Educational theories and teaching methods must respond to new ways of employing technologies and how it can be effectively integrated into learners' education. Educational procedures, tactics, and approaches are based on a variety of theories. They do, however, continue to use traditional learning methods. The action research (Mwanza & Engeström, 2005) is a theoretical framework that has aided the creation of innovative pedagogies. The communication between humans and computers is the emphasis of this theoretical approach. It was crucial in the growth of learning through the use of instruments, tools, mediation, and other methods. This idea emphasises the potential impact of new technologies as vehicles for modernising, contextualising, and altering activity routines on teaching and learning (Engestrom, 1987). Vygotsky (1978) was interested in the evolution of learning and social interaction (Cole & Wertsch, 1996). Vygotsky's concepts in terms of innovation learning and career contextual learning were investigated by Attwell (2010, a). According to Coffield (2008), there is no "compelling evidence that learners can be categorized into four groups based on their learning preferences: visual, aural, kinaesthetic, or tactile." he continued (p.32) "This trend gives its adherents the appearance of student-centered teaching, and it conveniently shifts the blame for students' failure."

4. Methodology

The goal of this research is to discover the obstacles faced by university students during the shift to online education in the second semester of the COVID-19 programme, as well as to investigate possible remedies and recommendations for future virtual learning.

5. Participant

The research was carried out in the–University for English language learners at the undergraduate level. It was carried out following the completion of virtual teaching courses and during the second semester's final tests. The sample consisted of 100 students, with 55 males and 45 females pursuing bachelor's degrees in English. The English department has the most college students, while the other departments have a small number of students. The majority of the students have never taken an online course before. Although the students opted for the online classes available, the assessments were held in person.

6. Results

The data was analyzed using descriptive research methodologies, and the study's findings focused on four main factors:

- Using the Blackboard tool's available activities and services.
- Alternatives to Blackboard that are used during online learning.
- The difficulties and roadblocks encountered while taking online English classes.

During COVID-19, learners' experience with face-to-face virtual learning. The learners' ability to use all of Blackboard's features for online learning activities was the first study question. According to the findings, 69.80 percent of students could use all of Blackboard's online learning programmes. They were able to enrol in online classes, participate actively, submit assignments, and take exams. 10.50 percent of students could only attend classes, 7.80 percent could only attend and participate in lectures, but they couldn't submit assignments or take exams online, 4.50 percent of students could attend, participate in, and submit projects, and 7.20 percent couldn't do any of the above using the Chalk board platform.

During COVID-19, the percentage of people who used the Blackboard platform for online English study is shown in the image below.

When some students were unable to access the Blackboard application, the second study question was regarding the alternative tools they used. Homework and other given activities were sent and received via WhatsApp. Some professors utilized WhatsApp to conduct classes; the biggest number, 72 percent, chose WhatsApp, while the second alternative medium, emails, received 53.60 percent. Zoom was the third platform, with a 33.50 percent share. Other platforms, such as Google Classroom and Microsoft Team, were used by 24% of the participants. Figure 2 shows the percentages of operating platforms and technologies other than Blackboard used in online courses during the COVID-19 outbreak.

The research question concerned the stated issues and impediments; the first being internet speed, which affects around 48 percent of learners. Only 18 percent of learners had no problems when completing their e-learning. The score for online access and material downloading is 14%. Difficulties in performing online exams received a 13

percent grade because some students were unable to access the online exams or had internet connectivity issues. The average score for each lab session is 8%. These online learning-related challenges are addressed in Figure 3:

The final research question focuses on how satisfied learners were with online courses during in the pandemic. Online learning satisfied 43.20 percent of students, while 42.90 percent were satisfied with certain preservations. 13.80% of students were dissatisfied with their online education.

7. Discussion

The goal of this study was to look into the challenges that learners encounter when it comes to online education during the current epidemic. E-learning problems, learners' engagement with technology tools in e-learning, and learners' satisfaction with online learning are a few of these issues. According to the findings, many pupils (more than 30%) missed several chores, responsibilities, and interactions with teachers, all of which are critical in the educational process. The findings revealed certain technical challenges with utilising the Chalk board tool, including such online course access, class materials download, audio, and video playback, which is consistent with Alturise's (2020) study, which found concern over the technical issue's resolution. The study concluded that help desk support is required to ensure online learning is reliable. During the crisis, teachers and students were compelled to address this issue and use other virtual learning platforms for uninterrupted study. They used email to submit their projects, Microsoft Teams, Google, and the Zoom platform to conduct certain lectures owing to the course not being available in Blackboard at the start of the transition or students being unable to check in to Blackboard. . Furthermore, the majority of students used the WhatsApp network for online learning. Because most

students utilised their phones in this context, the access to mobile phones aided the success of online learning. The findings of this study corroborate (Kaid & Bin-Hady 2019) findings, which confirmed the influence of just using social media platforms in learning and advocated for their activation in English language learning.

Conclusion

The study's goal is to look into and research the challenges and issues that COVID-19 learners have when it comes to online learning. At the time of the epidemic, synchronized e-learning was the remedy. However, it had a negative impact on students' performance and learning outcomes. The study discovered that students had difficulty accessing the Blackboard platform. During online learning, about 30% of students skipped classes and other tasks because they were using Blackboard, and they switched to other programmes. The study found that technological concerns were the biggest hurdles that learners faced when it came to online learning. Some students had issues with internet connectivity, accessing lessons, and downloading course materials.

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